

22RPT04 RFMicrowave2

D3: Improved calibration method for the calibration of monopole antennas by the equivalent capacitance substitution method (ECSM) and loop antennas by TAM and Helmholtz coils

Organisation name of the lead participant for the deliverable: SIQ

Due date of the deliverable: 31 December 2025

Actual submission date of the deliverable: 31 March 2026

Confidentiality Status: PU - Public, fully open

Deliverable Cover Sheet

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The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

European Partnership Co-funded by the European Union

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Suggestion for the quotation of the references:

Marko Berginc, Mats Cedheim, Tomáš Pavlíček, Roberto Guarino, "Improved calibration method for the calibration of monopole antennas by the equivalent capacitance substitution method (ECSM) and loop antennas by TAM and Helmholtz coils," *Zenodo*, March 2026, doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20020509>

Summary

This report originated within the project 22RPT04 RFMicrowave2 (Development of RF and microwave metrology capability II), a EURAMET project running between May 2023 and April 2026. It discusses an improved calibration method for the calibration of monopole antennas by the equivalent capacitance substitution method (ECSM) and loop antennas by TAM and Helmholtz coils. The methods have been implemented in several laboratories of the project partners (SIQ, RISE, CMI) and the experience of involved partners will be used for further development of this method and commercial deployment of these methods. Project partner KORAL helped to improve the report.

Acknowledgement

The project (22RPT04 RFMicrowave2) has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

For further details about the RFMicrowave 2 project see the project website <https://rfmwii.cmi.gov.cz/>

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1 Introduction

The accurate calibration of antennas used for electromagnetic compatibility measurements in the low-frequency range remains a demanding metrological task, particularly where conventional far-field methods are not applicable and where the interaction between the antenna, its matching network, the surrounding environment, and the measurement configuration must be carefully controlled. This deliverable addresses these challenges by presenting improved calibration methods for two important antenna categories used in EMC measurements below 30 MHz, namely monopole antennas and loop antennas. The work has been developed with the aim of supporting traceable, reproducible, and practically implementable calibration procedures suitable for laboratory use.

For monopole antennas, the deliverable focuses on calibration by the Equivalent Capacitance Substitution Method (ECSM), which offers a practical alternative to plane-wave calibration for selected antenna types operating in the low-frequency region. Monopole antennas are typically used in the frequency range from 9 kHz to 30 MHz, where the wavelength is large compared with the antenna dimensions and where standard far-field antenna calibration techniques are generally unsuitable. In such cases, calibration is commonly performed using a plane-wave method above a large ground plane, but the result may be influenced by the geometry of the antenna matching unit, grounding details, and the practical mounting arrangement. The ECSM approach addresses this by replacing the monopole rod with an equivalent capacitance representing the self-capacitance of the radiating element, thereby enabling calibration of the matching unit under controlled laboratory conditions.

A central objective of this deliverable is to define the conditions under which the ECSM method can be applied with confidence and to describe the key factors that determine its metrological performance. These include the design and realization of the dummy adapter, the selection and characterization of the equivalent capacitance, the configuration of the measurement setup, and the treatment of relevant uncertainty contributions. Particular attention is given to practical implementation issues such as adapter geometry, electrical bonding, connector arrangement, and the use of either vector network analyser-based or signal generator and receiver-based measurement configurations. In addition, the document considers the limits of applicability of the method, especially for longer monopole structures or configurations involving counterpoise or tripod mounting, where plane-wave calibration may remain the more appropriate approach.

For loop antennas, the deliverable addresses the determination of magnetic antenna factor using the Three Antenna Method (TAM), a method based on a reference loop antenna, and complementary calibration approaches using Helmholtz coils and TEM cells. Loop antennas are widely used for magnetic field measurements in EMC testing over the frequency range from 9 kHz to 30 MHz, but their calibration is complicated by the difficulty of generating ideal low-frequency plane-wave conditions and by the sensitivity of the result to antenna geometry, alignment, and environmental influences. The TAM approach provides an absolute method based on pairwise measurements among three loop antennas, while the reference-antenna method offers a practical route to direct traceability when a calibrated standard loop antenna is available. The alternative methods based on Helmholtz coils and TEM cells are included to extend applicability, particularly in situations where VNA-based loop calibration becomes limited by weak coupling, low sensitivity, or increasing measurement uncertainty at the lowest frequencies.

An important aspect of the work presented in this deliverable is the consistent integration of uncertainty evaluation with the calibration procedures themselves. For monopole antenna calibration, the analysis covers contributions associated with voltage measurement, mismatch, equivalent capacitance selection, effective height, and the characteristics of the matching unit. For loop antenna calibration, the uncertainty treatment includes dimensional measurements, antenna alignment, environmental effects, limitations of coupling approximations, field non-uniformity, and the uncertainty of transmission measurements. By addressing these factors explicitly, the deliverable supports the establishment of uncertainty budgets and improves the comparability of calibration results between laboratories.

Traceability is treated as a core metrological requirement throughout the document. The described methods are linked to calibrated dimensional measurements, capacitance and impedance measurements, VNA and receiver-based electrical measurements, and reference standards maintained within accredited calibration frameworks. This ensures that the resulting antenna factors are supported by an unbroken chain of measurements to recognized standards and are suitable for use in accredited EMC and antenna calibration activities.

Overall, this deliverable provides a structured and practically oriented contribution to the improvement of low-frequency antenna calibration methods. By combining method development, implementation guidance, uncertainty analysis, and traceability considerations, it supports the establishment of more robust calibration procedures for monopole and loop antennas used in EMC applications. The results are intended to strengthen measurement consistency across laboratories and to contribute to improved confidence in radiated disturbance measurements performed in the low-frequency range.

2 Calibration of monopole antenna using equivalent capacitance substitution method

2.1 Theory

Monopole antennas usually consist of monopole rod (*i.e.*, the radiating element) and the matching unit which is a metal housing containing active/passive connection between the monopole radiating element (*i.e.*, metal rod) and the input of a measuring receiver, Fig. 1. The matching unit can also contain a matching circuit and amplifier. Good electrical contact of the metal base of the housing with the ground plane is necessary for effective and reproducible performance of the monopole antenna. Antennas with rubber feet usually also have a metal foot which ensures good electrical contact with a ground plane. The units without a metal foot uses a short metal braid strip (width at least 15 mm) which is in good electric contact with the ground plane.

Figure 1: An example of monopole antenna with a matching unit and radiating rod

Monopole antennas are typically used at lower frequencies (typical frequency range between 9 kHz and 30 MHz). The wavelengths in this frequency range are very long therefore usual methods (standard antenna method, three antenna method, *etc.*) for antenna calibration that rely on far-field could not be used. Instead, monopole antennas are usually calibrated using a plane wave method where the entire antenna is illuminated by a plane wave above a large ground plane. The matching units is in most cases above the ground plane however, the taller housings have greater effect on the measured antenna factors AF .

On the contrary, the monopole antennas could be calibrated with *Equivalent Capacitor Substitution Method* (ECSM) where a rod is substituted by a capacitor equal to the self-capacitance of the rod. Therefore, each model of monopole antenna requires the design of dummy antenna (*i.e.*, an adapter containing a capacitor). **The ECSM can work only for antennas whose total length from the base of the matching unit to the top of the rod is shorter than $\lambda/8$.** Additionally, monopole antennas are sometimes mounted on a counterpoise (*e.g.*, a vestigial ground plate of dimension 0.6 m by 0.6 m) on a tripod and the AF can be in this case several dB lower than the AF measured with the matching unit on the ground plane or by the ECSM. These antennas are usually used outdoors, and they can be accurately calibrated only by the plane wave method. Alternatively, the vestigial ground plane could be connected to a conducting bench earthed to a wall in a shielded room, or by following other manufacturer's recommendations regarding the use of counterpoise or ground plane, bonding (*i.e.*, earthing) the antenna matching unit to the ground plane *etc.*

The calibration of monopole antennas is usually performed between 9 kHz and 30 MHz, or even up to 100 MHz if an antenna is specified in this frequency range. The number of frequency points should be large enough so a smooth curve could be obtained. Generally, increments defined in each frequency range (Table 1) should satisfy this requirement.

Table 1: Frequency points where the calibration of monopole antennas should be performed

Frequency range	Increments
9 kHz to 10 kHz	1 kHz
10 kHz to 150 kHz	10 kHz
150 kHz to 200 kHz	50 kHz
200 kHz to 1 MHz	100 kHz
1 MHz to 30 MHz	1 MHz

The antenna factor AF of monopole antenna is defined by Eq.1 in linear form and by Eq. 2 in logarithmic form, where the V_D denotes the measured output of the signal generator in V or dB(μ V), V_L measured output of the matching unit given in V or dB(μ V) and L_h the height correction factor (for the effective height) given in meters or dB(m). The height correction factor L_h in dB(m) and effective height of the rod h_e in meters are calculated using Eqs. 3 and 4 respectively, where λ denotes the wavelength of the signal (*i.e.*, $\lambda=c/f$), where c denoted the speed of light ($2.998 \cdot 10^8$ m/s), f the frequency of the signal and h the actual height (length) of the rod in meters. The effective length h_e thus expresses the relation between the voltage induced in the antenna V_M and the vertical component of incident E . Typical frequency dependence of L_h for 1-meter-long rod antenna is shown in Fig. 2.

$$AF = \frac{E}{V_m} = \frac{V_D}{V_L} \cdot \frac{1}{h_e}, \text{ in m}^{-1} \quad (1)$$

$$AF = V_D - V_L - L_h + \Delta U_{dB} \quad (2)$$

$$L_h = 20 \cdot \log(h_e) \quad (3)$$

$$h_e = \frac{\lambda}{2 \cdot \pi} \tan \frac{\pi \cdot h}{\lambda} \quad (4)$$

$$L_h = 20 \cdot \log \left(h_e + \frac{h_b}{2} \right) \quad (5)$$

Figure 2: Frequency dependence of L_h in dB for 1-meter-long rod antenna

The ECSM does not consider the contribution of the matching unit to the AF ; if the matching unit is used above the ground plane this will yield in decreased AF due to increased effective height L_h . An empirical correction is to add half the height of the housing to the rod length when calculation the height correction factor L_h , Eq. 5, where h_b denotes the height of the matching unit. A typical reduction of AF is 0.8 dB. However, when calibrating a monopole antenna which is used according to CISPR 25 (*i.e.*, the matching unit is placed beneath the ground plane), Eq. 3 without the h_b correction should be used.

The capacitance C_a of the dummy capacitor (*i.e.*, self-capacitance of the rod above infinite ground plane) is calculated using Eq. 6 (in pF), where a denotes the average radius of the rod in meters (special attention should be taken on the average radius a of the telescopic antennas since the antenna's radius changes along the rod's length). The C_a increases with increasing length and radius of the rod. Frequency dependent part of Eq. 6 comes close to unity when $h < \lambda/8$ condition is met therefore this part could generally neglected. On the contrary, the capacitance C_a increases quite sharply at higher frequencies when $h > \lambda/8$.

$$C_a = \frac{55.6 \cdot h}{\ln(h/a) - 1} \cdot \frac{\tan(2 \cdot \pi \cdot h/\lambda)}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot h/\lambda} \quad (6)$$

Monopole antennas with a 1-meter-long rod are commonly used in EMC measurements. It has 0.5 m effective height h_e , which correspond to -6 dB(m) height correction factor L_h . The self-capacitance C_a for this antenna is 12 pF assuming the rod radius of 3.6 mm.

Note 1: The Eqs. 1-5 are valid only for cylindrical rods shorter than $\lambda/8$

Note 2: The telescopic monopole antennas should be calibrated at the length that is requested by the customer or at the length for which the manufacturer's specifications apply.

Note 3: A plane wave method only should be used for calibration of monopole antennas that are placed on tripods.

The ECSM adapters typically contain just the capacitor. However, on the market one can find commercial ESCM adapter which contains resistor(s) in addition to the capacitor. One example is shown in Fig. 3 where a Schwarzbeck CA 9243 calibration adapter is shown and the electrical circuit that is inside. This resistor on one hand provided better matching with the measuring equipment which is usually 50 Ω based but on the other hand additional resistor also changes the calculation of AF , Eq. 2. In these cases, manufacturers provide the correction factor ΔUdB (dB) that needs to be included in the calculation of AF . Moreover, the ECSM adapters containing just the capacitor might not be perfectly designed, and some resistive losses might be present. In these cases, ΔUdB should be also included as a correction of AF calculation and/or included in the uncertainty budget. However, if the adapter is purely capacitive, ΔUdB and its corresponding uncertainty can be assumed as 0.

Figure 3: Commercial Schwarzbeck CA 9243 calibration adapter (left) and corresponding equivalent circuit which has integrated 50 Ω resistor. The manufacturer defined how the calculation of AF should be modified due to the resistor.

2.2 Dummy capacitor

The structure of the dummy capacitor is shown in Fig. 4. The capacitance C_a equals to the capacitance of the actual rod when placed above infinite ground plate.

Figure 4: An adaptor containing dummy capacitor that is used for monopole antenna calibration with ECSM method

Several conditions should be met when constructing the adaptor:

- The capacitor used as equivalent capacitance in the dummy antenna should be mounted in a small metal box or on a small metal frame. The leads shall be no longer than 8 mm and kept close to the surface of the metal box frame.
- Capacitance C_a should be calculated using Eq. 6. A silver mica capacitor with 5% tolerance is recommended. The capacitor leads should be as short as possible to reduce inductance. The length should not be longer than 8 mm and they should be at least 10 mm from the surface of the metal mount. Connecting wires should be also far enough from the adaptor shell or ground plane of the monopole to avoid capacitive coupling that distorts the calculated impedance of the adaptor.
- S lead spacing should be between 5 mm and 10 mm (10 mm from all surfaces if enclosed in a box)
- L lead lengths (both ends) should be as short as possible, but not longer than 8 mm. Total lead length (including both leads of the capacitor and the length of connector that mate with the rod input of the matching unit) should not be greater than 40 mm.
- The connector that mate with the antenna port (matching unit) should be placed on dielectric material. The connector should have low inductance. It should be also placed at least 10 mm away from any metallic part of the mounting frame. The connector could be in the form of threaded brass bold which can be screwed into antenna port of the matching unit.
- The mounting frame of the adaptor (metal part) should be electrically connected to the metal matching unit by at least 15 mm wide metal braid to ensure low inductance. If the entire mounting frame is dielectric then the outer conductor of connector A (either N-type or BNC) should be similarly connected to the matching unit by a braid.
- Any matching network incorporated into a dummy antenna shall be evaluated for losses associated with resistive voltage dividers and these shall be accounted for as ΔU_{dB} (dB) in the calculation of the AF (Eq. 2).

2.3 Calibration setups

Two measurements setups could be used when calibrating monopole antennas using ECSM, *i.e.*, a method based on VNA measurements, Fig. 6 and a method based on signal generator and measuring receiver, Fig. 7. Equivalent model for both measurements is shown in Fig. 5.

When a monopole antenna receives a plane wave field E (in $\mu\text{V}/\text{m}$) it induces an RF voltage source $h_e \cdot E$ (in μV) and generate an RF voltage V_M (in μV) at the input of the measuring receiver (or Port 2 of a VNA). The C_a (in pF) in the equivalent model simulate the reactance of the radiating element of the antenna (*i.e.*, the rod). The antenna matching unit is represented by a chain matrix (ABCD).

Figure 5: Equivalent model of measurement

Method based on VNA measurement

Measuring procedure:

- Connect the network analyser with the cables to be used in the measurements, Fig. 6. A 10 dB attenuator could be connected to Port 2 of the VNA to reduce mismatch losses. The length, insertion loss and the type of the cables connected between (i.) the T-connector port A and the port V_D and (ii.) between the 50 Ω port R and the port V_L shall be very similar (the loss difference shall be less than 0.1 dB). Voltage measurements shall be made at the port V_D and the port V_L .
- Set up the matching unit to be characterized and the measuring equipment as shown in Fig. 6. The dummy antenna should be connected as close to the antenna port as possible, and the T-connector should be connected as close as possible to the dummy antenna.
- To achieve the highest accuracy possible, perform a 12-term error correction of the VNA at the end of the cable. This will eliminate the source and load match errors (*i.e.*, mismatch contributions), therefore matching pads are not required. If only one-term error correction is used (*i.e.*, just thru correction) the 10 dB attenuator at the Port 2 of the VNA is recommended.
- Subtract the signal level V_L in dB(μ V) from the signal level V_D in dB(μ V) to obtain AF in dB(m^{-1}), Eq. 2. If necessary (depending on the calibration adapters), subtract L_h (approximately -6 dB).

Figure 6: A measuring set-up for monopole antenna calibration with ECSM method with VNA

Signal generator / measuring receiver method

Measuring procedure:

- Set-up the matching unit to be characterised and the measuring equipment as shown in Fig. 7. It is strongly recommended to use an attenuator (*e.g.*, 10 dB) between the RF generator and T-connector to reduce mismatch.
- With the equipment connected as shown and a 50 Ω termination of the T-connector, measure the received signal voltage V_L in dB(μ V) at the 50 Ω port R.
- Leaving the RF output of the signal generator unchanged, transfer the 50 Ω termination to the 50 Ω port R and transfer the receiver input cable to the T-connector. Measure the drive signal voltage V_D in dB(μ V).
- Subtract V_L from V_D to obtain AF in dB(m^{-1}), Eq. 2. If necessary (depending on the calibration adapters), subtract L_h (approximately -6 dB).

Figure 7: A measuring set-up for monopole antenna calibration with ECSM method with signal generator and measuring receiver

General considerations

Several other general considerations should be met when using either VNA method or method that is based on signal generator/measuring receiver (signal analyser) method:

- The $50\ \Omega$ termination used in the calibration is recommended to have a return loss greater than 32 dB (*i.e.*, $VSWR > 1.05$). This requirement is on one hand easily achievable and on the other hand gives small uncertainty contribution.
- The measuring receiver or the VNA shall have a return loss greater than 20.9 dB (*i.e.*, $VSWR < 1.2$).
- The output of the signal generator or VNA should be stable in frequency and amplitude.
- The dummy antenna should be connected as close as possible to the antenna port of the matching unit. T-connector should be connected as close as possible to the dummy antenna. The outer conductor of the T-connector shall be electrically connected to the matching unit, if necessary, preferably by using a short flat braid.
- The matching unit shall be earthed via the outer conductor of the coaxial cable to the measuring receiver or VNA. If the return losses of the receiver/signal generator or VNA are high, additional pads may not be needed at the receiver input port and generator output port or VNA's input and output ports.

2.4 Uncertainty calculation

The parameter of interest when calibrating monopole antennas is antenna factor AF . Mathematical model of measurement when measured with signal generator and measuring receiver (or signal analyser) in dB is defined by Eq. 7. Mathematical model of measurement when measured with VNA in dB is defined by Eq. 8. Both mathematical models are valid only for the antennas having rods shorted than 1.2 m.

$$AF = (V_D + \delta V_{D,meas} + \delta V_{D,MM}) - (V_L + \delta V_{L,meas} + \delta V_{L,MM} + \delta V_{L,Ca} + \delta V_{L,amp}) - (L_h + \delta L_{L,h}) + \Delta U_{dB} \quad (7)$$

$$AF = (\Delta V + \delta \Delta V_{meas} + \delta \Delta V_{D,MM} - \delta \Delta V_{L,MM} - \delta V_{L,Ca} - \delta V_{L,amp}) - (L_h + \delta L_{L,h}) + \Delta U_{dB} \quad (8)$$

Description of the symbols:

AF	<i>Antenna Factor</i> , the parameter under calibration
V_D	measured output of the Port 1 of the VNA or signal generator in dB(V)
V_L	measured output of the matching unit in dB(V)
ΔV	voltage difference $V_D - V_L$ when measured with VNA
$\delta V_{D,meas}$	the effects of the characteristics on measured V_D
$\delta V_{L,meas}$	the effects of the characteristics on measured V_L
$\delta V_{D,MM}$	change in V_D caused by the mismatch in cable connection
$\delta V_{L,MM}$	change in V_L caused by the mismatch in cable connection
$\delta V_{L,Ca}$	effect of small changes in the antenna capacitance C_a
$\delta V_{L,amp}$	effect of the gain of the matching unit amplifier (if present)
L_h	height correction factor in dB(m)
$\delta L_{L,h}$	effect on the L_h caused by deviation of h_e from expected value
ΔU_{dB}	Resistive losses in the adapter

Measured voltage in dB(V), V_D

The V_D is the voltage measured on Port 2 of the VNA or at the input of the measuring receiver or measured voltage at the input port of the signal analyser. The voltage represents the input voltage to the dummy capacitor (*i.e.*, dummy antenna). The value is assumed to be exact. All corresponding uncertainties are included in the $\delta V_{D,meas}$ parameter.

Measured voltage in dB(V), V_L

The V_L is the voltage measured on Port 2 of the VNA or at the input of the measuring receiver or measured voltage at the input port of the signal analyser. The voltage represents the output voltage from the matching unit. The value is assumed to be exact. All corresponding uncertainties are included in the $\delta V_{L,meas}$ parameter.

Voltage difference, ΔV

When a VNA is used, the voltage difference could be correctly measured by a single measurement where the voltage difference ΔV in dB(μ V) is defined by Eq. 9. The value is assumed to be exact. All corresponding uncertainties are included in the $\delta V_{\Delta,meas}$ parameter.

$$\Delta V = V_D - V_L \quad (9)$$

The effects of the characteristics on measured V_L and V_D , $\delta V_{L,meas}$ and $\delta V_{D,meas}$

The $\delta V_{D,meas}$ and $\delta V_{L,meas}$ represents the effects of the characteristics of the input port of the measuring receiver (or signal analyser) on measured V_D and V_L , respectively. Those two parameters are valid only when calibration is done by a signal generator and measuring receiver (or signal analyser). The $V_{L,meas}$ and $\delta V_{D,meas}$ are calculated using Eqs. 10 and 11, respectively. They both include the linearity and resolution (*i.e.*, $\delta V_{D,L,linear}$ and $\delta V_{D,L,res}$, respectively). Probability distribution is assumed to be normal. Sensitivity coefficient c_x is 1.

$$\delta V_{D,meas} = \delta V_{D,linear} + \delta V_{D,res} \quad (10)$$

$$\delta V_{L,meas} = \delta V_{L,linear} + \delta V_{L,res} \quad (11)$$

The effects of the characteristics on measured difference ΔV , $\delta V_{\Delta,meas}$

The $\delta V_{\Delta,meas}$ represents the effect of the VNA (noise, drift, linearity, resolution, Eq. 12), cables (reflection, attenuation, tracking symmetry) and types of connectors (reflection, tracking symmetry) on the uncertainty of measured ΔV . This uncertainty is estimated from analysis of calibration of $|s_{21}|$ parameter. Typical values for the measured $|s_{21}|$ parameters for BNC and N-type of connectors for different attenuations in dB in frequency range between 9 kHz to 30 MHz is given in Table 2. The uncertainty distribution is assumed to be normal with a coverage factor $k = 2$. Sensitivity coefficient c_x is 1. However, this uncertainty contribution is relatively small compared to other contribution therefore it could be also neglected in some cases.

$$\delta V_{\Delta,meas} = \delta V_{\Delta,noise} + \delta V_{\Delta,drift} + \delta V_{\Delta,linear} + \delta V_{\Delta,res} \quad (12)$$

Table 2: Typical uncertainties for attenuation measurement for different attenuations. The uncertainty is assumed to be normal with coverage factor $k=2$. The typical uncertainties are valid for BNC and N-type connectors in a frequency range between 9 kHz to 30 MHz.

Attenuation $ s_{21} $ parameter	Typical uncertainty
0 dB to -30 dB	0.06 dB
-30 dB to -50 dB	0.08 dB
-50 dB to -100 dB	0.18 dB

Change in V_D and V_L , respectively caused by the mismatch in cable connection, $\delta V_{D,MM}$ and $\delta V_{L,MM}$

The terms $\delta V_{D,MM}$ and $\delta V_{L,MM}$ are changes in V_D and V_L , respectively, caused by the mismatch in cable connection. Both parameters in dB are defined by Eqs. 13 and 14, respectively. For $\Gamma_M = \Gamma_A = \Gamma_T = 0.06$ (*i.e.*,

24 dB return loss), $s_{11} = 0.18$ (15 dB return loss), $s_{22} = 0.32$ (10 dB return loss) and $s_{21} = 1.0$, yields $M_D^- = M_L^- = 0.266$ dB. The uncertainty distribution is assumed to be U-shaped. Sensitivity coefficient c_x is 1.

$$M_D^\pm = 20 \cdot \log \left[1 \pm (|\Gamma_T| \cdot |s_{11}| + |\Gamma_M| \cdot |s_{22}| + |\Gamma_T| \cdot |\Gamma_M| \cdot |s_{11}| \cdot |s_{22}| + |\Gamma_T| \cdot |\Gamma_M| \cdot |s_{21}|^2) \right] \quad (13)$$

$$M_L^\pm = 20 \cdot \log \left[1 \pm (|\Gamma_A| \cdot |s_{11}| + |\Gamma_M| \cdot |s_{22}| + |\Gamma_A| \cdot |\Gamma_M| \cdot |s_{11}| \cdot |s_{22}| + |\Gamma_A| \cdot |\Gamma_M| \cdot |s_{21}|^2) \right] \quad (14)$$

The effect of small changes in the antenna capacitance and the effect of the gain of the matching unit amplifier (if present), $\delta V_{L,Ca}$ and $\delta V_{L,amp}$

$\delta V_{L,Ca}$ and $\delta V_{L,amp}$ are the results of small changes in the antenna capacitance C_a and the gain of the matching unit amplifier (if present). To estimate this uncertainty contribution, the dimension of the rod needs to be measured first (*i.e.*, the length of the rod h and the diameter of the rod $d=2 \times a$) and calculate the expected (ideal) value of the dummy capacitor C_a , which should be ideally used for the calibration, Eq. 6. In the second step, the most appropriate ECSM adapter should be chosen from all available adapters, Figs. 8 and 9. The *criterion* is finding the smallest RMS error between the measured C_a' and ideal capacitance C_a , Eq. 15, among all available ECSM adapters, Fig. 8.

$$RMS_{diff} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \cdot \sum_{f=9kHz}^{30MHz} (C_a(f_i) - C_a'(f_i))^2} \quad (15)$$

Figure 8: The capacitance of 13 different ECSM adapters as measured in 2025.

Figure 9: A set of ECSM adapters which can be used for monopole antenna calibration.

The measured capacitance of the ECSM adaptor that is used during the calibration (*i.e.*, C_a') should be taken from the latest calibration certificate. The capacitance C_a' could be accurately measured in a frequency range between 9 kHz and 2 MHz using LCR meter. The C_a' at higher frequencies ($f > 2$ MHz) could be measured by Impedance Analyzer (*e.g.*, Keysight E4990A). Alternatively, the capacitance could be directly and un-accredited measured with VNA (*e.g.*, Agilent E5061B) using parallel capacitance equivalent model. Alternatively, the manufacturer's specification could be also used if commercial adaptors are used. Finally, both capacitances, *i.e.*, C_a and C_a' are then used in Eq. 16 to estimate the uncertainty contribution $\delta V_{L,Ca}$ given in dB with rectangular uncertainty distribution. Sensitivity coefficient c_x is 1. Typically (according to CISPR 16-1-6 standard), this uncertainty contributions equals 1.09 dB.

$$\delta V_{L,Ca} = F'_a - F_a = 20 \cdot \log \frac{\Phi'}{\Phi} \approx 20 \cdot \log \left(\frac{C_a'}{C_a} \right) = 20 \cdot \log \left(\frac{C_a}{C_a + \varepsilon_C} \right) \quad (16)$$

Note 1: If a capacitance 12.6 pF is used instead of 10 pF this will yield about 2 dB error in AF calibration.

The effect on the L_h caused by deviation of h_e from expected value, $\delta L_{L,h}$

The $\delta L_{L,h}$ is the effect on the height correction factor which is caused by deviation of the h_e of the antenna from expected value. The correction in dB is defined by Eq. 17 where h_e' denotes the deviation of h_e from expected value and the x_{he} presents the relative change in h_e whereas the L_h' represents the change of L_h due to the change of resultant capacitance. The procedure described above uses an expression for effective height that includes $\tan(x)$ factor. At low frequency the monopole effective length may be assumed as half of the physical length. For the heights greater than $h > \lambda/8$ this $\tan(x)$ increasingly significantly corrects h_e . However, the errors became large as the frequency approaches resonance. Assuming the $\tan(x)$ correction is applied, it is estimated that the effective height of rods up to 1.1 m may be calculated with 4% uncertainty below 35 MHz. This estimation includes uncertainty in the extra apparent height added by the attachment point. Accordingly, an error of 4% in the effective height causes an error of 0.34 dB in L_h with rectangular probability distribution. Sensitivity coefficient c_x is 1.

$$L_h' - L_h = 20 \cdot \log \left(\frac{h_e'}{h_e} \right) = 20 \cdot \log(1 + x_{he}) \quad (17)$$

Some monopole antennas are specified for use up-to 100 MHz (*i.e.*, the heights exceeding $h > \lambda/8$). In this case, the ECSM method is not suitable, and antennas should be calibrated solely by a plane wave method.

2.5 Uncertainty calculation examples

Table 3 shown ideal example of uncertainty calculation when calculated value of equivalent capacitor matches almost perfectly with the measured value. On contrary, a more realistic examples are shown in Tables 4-6. The overall standards uncertainties (normal distribution, $k = 2$) ranges between 0.7 dB when a perfect match is obtained between the measured and calculated capacitor and it could be typically around 1.2 dB or even up to 1.7 dB if a good match is not obtained. As shown above it is quite critical to produce a large set of different ESCM, to obtain relatively good matching capacitor for each calculated capacitance a .

Table 3: An example for Antenna Factor (AF) calibration for 1-meter-long monopole antenna at 9 kHz (diameter is 25 mm), i.e., ideal case where the equivalent capacitance of DUT antenna matches almost perfectly with calibration adapter. The antenna was calibrated using equivalent capacitance substitution method ECSM and VNA using Schwarzbeck CA 9243 calibration adapter which has 16.24 pF thru capacitance at measured frequency.

Mathematical model of measurement:								
ΔV	-15,95 dB							
L_h	-6,021 dB	$AF = (\Delta V + \delta\Delta V_{meas} + \delta\Delta V_{D,MM} - \delta\Delta V_{L,MM} - \delta V_{L,Ca} - \delta V_{L,amp}) - (L_h + \delta L_{L,h})$						
f	9 kHz							
λ	33333 m							
d	25 mm							
l	100 cm							
C_a	16,26 pF							
C_a'	16,24 pF							
Quantity	Estimate	Standard uncertainty	Probability distribution	Div.	Sensitivity coefficient	Uncertainty contribution	Effective degr. Of freedom	
X_i	x_i	$u(x_i)$			c_i	$u_i(y)$	v_i	
ΔV	-15,95 dB	0,03 dB	normal	2	1 /	0,03 dB	5	
$\delta V_{D,MM}$	0 dB	0,19 dB	U-shaped	1,41	1 /	0,19 dB	1E+99	
$\delta V_{L,MM}$	0 dB	0,19 dB	U-shaped	1,41	1 /	0,19 dB	1E+99	
$L_{L,h}$	-6,021 dB	0,20 dB	rectengular	1,73	1 /	0,20 dB	5	
$\delta V_{L,Ca}$	0 dB	0,01 dB	rectengular	1,73	1 /	0,01 dB	15	
$\delta V_{L,amp}$	0 dB	0 dB	normal	1	1 /	0 dB	1E+99	
AF	-9,93 dB	Calculated uncertainty:					0,33 dB	41
		Expanded uncertainty of measurement:					0,71 dB	

Table 4: An example for Antenna Factor (AF) calibration for 1-meter-long monopole antenna at 9 kHz (diameter is 16 mm). The antenna was calibrated using equivalent capacitance substitution method ECSM and VNA using calibration adapter which has 11.59 pF thru capacitance at measured frequency.

Mathematical model of measurement:								
ΔV	-15,95 dB							
L_h	-6,021 dB	$AF = (\Delta V + \delta\Delta V_{meas} + \delta\Delta V_{D,MM} - \delta\Delta V_{L,MM} - \delta V_{L,Ca} - \delta V_{L,amp}) - (L_h + \delta L_{L,h})$						
f	9 kHz							
λ	33333 m							
d	16 mm							
l	100 cm							
C_a	14,37 pF							
C_a'	14,59 pF							
Quantity	Estimate	Standard uncertainty	Probability distribution	Div.	Sensitivity coefficient	Uncertainty contribution	Effective degr. Of freedom	
X_i	x_i	$u(x_i)$			c_i	$u_i(y)$	v_i	
ΔV	-15,95 dB	0,03 dB	normal	2	1 /	0,03 dB	5	
$\delta V_{D,MM}$	0 dB	0,19 dB	U-shaped	1,41	1 /	0,19 dB	1E+99	
$\delta V_{L,MM}$	0 dB	0,19 dB	U-shaped	1,41	1 /	0,19 dB	1E+99	
$L_{L,h}$	-6,021 dB	0,20 dB	rectengular	1,73	1 /	0,20 dB	5	
$\delta V_{L,Ca}$	0 dB	0,08 dB	rectengular	1,73	1 /	0,08 dB	15	
$\delta V_{L,amp}$	0 dB	0 dB	normal	1	1 /	0 dB	1E+99	
AF	-9,93 dB	Calculated uncertainty:					0,34 dB	45
		Expanded uncertainty of measurement:					0,73 dB	

Table 5: An example for Antenna Factor (AF) calibration for 1-meter-long monopole antenna at 1 MHz (diameter is 16 mm). The antenna was calibrated using equivalent capacitance substitution method ECSM and VNA using calibration adapter which has 14.54 pF thru capacitance at measured frequency.

Mathematical model of measurement:								
ΔV	-15,95 dB							
L_h	-6,021 dB	$AF = (\Delta V + \delta\Delta V_{meas} + \delta\Delta V_{D,MM} - \delta\Delta V_{L,MM} - \delta V_{L,Ca} - \delta V_{L,amp}) - (L_h + \delta L_{L,h})$						
f	1000 kHz							
λ	300 m							
d	16 mm							
l	100 cm							
C_a	14,37 pF							
C_a'	14,54 pF							
Quantity	Estimate	Standard uncertainty	Probability distribution	Div.	Sensitivity coefficient	Uncertainty contribution	Effective degr. Of freedom	
X_i	x_i	$u(x_i)$			c_i	$u_i(y)$	v_i	
ΔV	-15,95 dB	0,03 dB	normal	2	1 /	0,03 dB	5	
$\delta V_{D,MM}$	0 dB	0,19 dB	U-shaped	1,41	1 /	0,19 dB	1E+99	
$\delta V_{L,MM}$	0 dB	0,19 dB	U-shaped	1,41	1 /	0,19 dB	1E+99	
$L_{L,h}$	-6,021 dB	0,20 dB	rectengular	1,73	1 /	0,20 dB	5	
$\delta V_{L,Ca}$	0 dB	0,06 dB	rectengular	1,73	1 /	0,06 dB	15	
$\delta V_{L,amp}$	0 dB	0 dB	normal	1	1 /	0 dB	1E+99	
AF	-9,93 dB	Calculated uncertainty:					0,34 dB	43
		Expanded uncertainty of measurement:					0,72 dB	

Table 6: An example for Antenna Factor (AF) calibration for 1-meter-long monopole antenna at 30 MHz (diameter is 16 mm). The antenna was calibrated using equivalent capacitance substitution method ECSM and VNA using calibration adapter which has 16.69 pF thru capacitance at measured frequency.

Mathematical model of measurement:								
ΔV	-15,95 dB							
L_h	-6,021 dB	$AF = (\Delta V + \delta\Delta V_{meas} + \delta\Delta V_{D,MM} - \delta\Delta V_{L,MM} - \delta V_{L,Ca} - \delta V_{L,amp}) - (L_h + \delta L_{L,h})$						
f	30000 kHz							
λ	10 m							
d	16 mm							
l	100 cm							
C_a	16,61 pF							
C_a'	16,69 pF							
Quantity	Estimate	Standard uncertainty	Probability distribution	Div.	Sensitivity coefficient	Uncertainty contribution	Effective degr. Of freedom	
X_i	x_i	$u(x_i)$			c_i	$u_i(y)$	v_i	
ΔV	-15,95 dB	0,03 dB	normal	2	1 /	0,03 dB	5	
$\delta V_{D,MM}$	0 dB	0,19 dB	U-shaped	1,41	1 /	0,19 dB	1E+99	
$\delta V_{L,MM}$	0 dB	0,19 dB	U-shaped	1,41	1 /	0,19 dB	1E+99	
$L_{L,h}$	-6,021 dB	0,20 dB	rectengular	1,73	1 /	0,20 dB	5	
$\delta V_{L,Ca}$	0 dB	0,02 dB	rectengular	1,73	1 /	0,02 dB	15	
$\delta V_{L,amp}$	0 dB	0 dB	normal	1	1 /	0 dB	1E+99	
AF	-9,93 dB	Calculated uncertainty:					0,33 dB	41
		Expanded uncertainty of measurement:					0,71 dB	

If a adapter with resistive losses is used, a typical uncertainty budget can be as shown in Table 7. The main addition, compared to the previous uncertainty calculations is the last uncertainty, which is from the estimation of the resistive losses in the adapter.

Table 7: Typical uncertainty budget for monopole antenna in the frequency range 9 kHz-30 MHz when ECSM adapter with resistive losses is used.

source of uncertainty	type (A or B)	value x_i	probability distribution	k -factor	sens. coeff. c_i	standard uncertainty contribution $u(x_i)$
VNA accuracy P_{in}	B	0.0116	Normal	2	1	0.0058
VNA temp drift P_{in}	B	0.0116	Normal	2	1	0.0058
VNA accuracy P_{out}	B	0.0116	Normal	2	1	0.0058
VNA temp drift P_{out}	B	0.0116	Normal	2	1	0.0058
Connector repeatability	A	0.0248	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.0143
Capacitor accuracy	B	0.2078	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.1200
Uncertainty from the rod dimensions	B	0.0404	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	2	0.0467
Mismatch	B	0.0093	U-shaped	$\sqrt{2}$	1	0.0066
Uncertainty in adapter losses	B	0.0114	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	2	0.0067
combined unc.						0.1304
expanded unc. ($k=2$) dB						1.07 dB

2.6 Traceability

The rod of monopole antenna should be measured with a reference calliper and reference ruler first. The measured geometry of the rod is used to calculate the capacitance of dummy capacitor which is integrated in adapter. The capacitance of adapter (dummy capacitor) is measured with LCR meter and Impedance Analyzer which should be both calibrated using reference AC voltage, reference time-base, reference resistors, capacitors and inductors.

The matching unit together with dummy adaptor is calibrated with either VNA or with the signal generator/measuring receiver (or spectral analyser) using the procedures related to s-parameter measurements or RF power measurements; the final traceability to international level is provided through calibration of reference termination (open, short, load) at other accredited laboratories.

3 Calibration of loop antennas by three antenna method (TAM)

3.1 Theory

The main parameter of antennas in general to be calibrated is antenna factor F_a (AF). Antennas are not calibrated in free space, since testing methods defined in CISPR 16-2-3 defines antenna should be located above a metallic ground plane at a height between 1 m and 4 m.

Antenna factor F_a in dB form is defined by Eq. 18:

$$F_a = E - V \text{ [dBm}^{-1}\text{]} \quad (18)$$

E field strength in dB(μ /m) of the incident plane wave that illuminates the antenna
 V resultant voltage in dB(μ V) across the output terminal of the antenna.

Antenna factor is dependent on the load connected to the antenna output. If there are any radiating elements radiating toward the load, its impedance also affects F_a . There are other factor affecting F_a as mutual coupling to its surroundings (e.g., proximity of other antennas, the ground, ...). When antenna is used in free-space environment, these effects are minimized. Output voltage on the output of antenna terminal is normally measured with a receiver, which is connected to antenna output terminal with a cable. Due to cable attenuation and mismatch connection (especially when cable has high VSWR), correction to the measurement must be made. When radiated emission measurement are performed, the incident field strength E can be calculated from V (output voltage on antenna terminal) and antenna factor F_a as $E=V + F_a$.

Loop antennas are used for EMC measurements for radiated disturbance measurements and are typically used in the frequency range from 9 kHz up to 30 MHz. Their typical diameter is up to 60 cm. Loop antenna is usually mounted on small box containing matching and tuning networks. Some also have an amplifier. To measure RF magnetic field strength with a loop antenna, its magnetic field antenna factor needs to be known. There are several techniques for the calibration of loop antennas (measuring its magnetic field antenna factor). The first method is TEM cell method that has advantage of wide frequency coverage, on the other hand it brings greater uncertainties of antenna factor. The second method is Helmholtz coil method, which is more accurate at frequencies up to 150 kHz. It can be also used conveniently for checking (validating) the TEM cell method at lower frequencies.

A well designed and manufactured loop antenna is symmetric in the plane of the loop and is shielded from picking up electric fields. Poor shielding can affect reproducibility of F_a in the calibration of loop antennas. Calibration methods are shown in the Table 8. This guide covers **Three Antenna Method** as an absolute method and **a method based on reference antenna** in the frequency range from 9 kHz to 30 MHz.

Table 8: Loop antenna calibration methods (VNA is Vector Network Analyser. Can also calibrate a combination of a signal generator and receiver).

	Name	Calibration instruments	No. of times measure	Note
Absolute calibration	TEM cell method	TEM cell Power meter Signal generator Receiver	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Determine the intensity of the magnetic field propagating in the TEM cell from the input power. - The size of the AUC is restricted by the size of the TEM cell - One measurement is enough
	Current measurement method	Transmitting loop (with thermocouple or current probe)	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - RF current through the element is measured, determining the strength of the magnetic field generated from the loop. Traceable with RF current. - Magnetic field strength depends on the input resistance of the thermocouple of current probe - One measurement is enough
	Three-antenna method	Three antennas VNA	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Traceable with RF attenuation - Must measure three times
Relative calibration	Substitution method	Transmitting loop Standard VNA	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If standard and AUC have different dimensions, then must compensate - Instead of the Standard, management of transmitting loop is required - Must measure two times (compare measurements)
	Magnetic field antenna factor method	Standard VNA	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Antenna with already known magnetic field antenna factor is used for transmitting antenna to generate magnetic field - One measurement is enough

3.2 Measurement of dimensional parameters

During the calibration of loop antennas several dimensional parameters must be determined. For each measured loop antenna its loop radius must be measured and the distance between the centres of both antennas. Additionally, we must ensure that the measured antenna pair is properly aligned.

Radius measurement of a loop antenna

The relevant radius that must be determined is the inner radius of the loop. The radius is shown in the Fig. 10.

Figure 10: Inner radius

The radius is measured with the calibrated beak scale. Radius is not measured directly, instead we measure the inner diameter of the loop. The measurement is repeated 5 times at different points, the uncertainty contributions are Type-A of the measured results, specification and resolution.

Antenna pair alignment

Measured antenna pair centres must be sufficiently aligned. We define sufficient alignment when the centres of both antennas are aligned within 1 cm from the ideal position. This is achieved by placing both antennas on tripods. The tripods are aligned in the same horizontal axis with the help of a straight rod that is inserted thru the attachments on the tripods. The height of the centres of both antennas is measured indirectly with the calibrated laser distance meter. The height is adjusted so that it is the same for both antenna centres. In this way alignment is also achieved for the vertical axis. Angle alignment is defined as the alignment of the planes of both antennas so that the misalignment angle is less than 5 degrees.

Distance measurement between loop antennas

When antennas alignment is achieved the distance between the centres of antennas is measured. The distance is measured with the calibrated laser meter. The distance between the antenna centres is then the sum of measured distance between the tripod's masts and the diameter of the masts or a direct distance between two antenna centres. Diameter of the masts is measured with a calibrated electronic calliper. This measurement again consists of Type-A uncertainty, resolution and specification. Additionally, a 5 mm uncertainty can be added due to the non-alignment of the setup.

3.3 Three antenna method (TAM)

The 3-antenna loop calibration method requires 3 loop antennas taken in pairs and yields the factors of each antenna separately. Unlike all the other standard methods, this method requires a VNA and the measurement of each loop antenna pair in turn as seen in Fig. 11.

The magnetic antenna factor of a loop antenna is defined as the ratio of the incident plane magnetic field strength to the output voltage across the load impedance (50 Ω). It is difficult to apply actual plane wave to a loop antenna and generate far-field conditions in the low frequency range. Also, evenly distributed magnetic field inside a loop antenna is not possible to achieve. For that reason, averaged magnetic field inside the receiving loop antenna is used instead of the ideal plane magnetic field. Averaged magnetic field is realized by a Three Antenna Method, when two loop antennas are set in parallel to each other in free space as shown in Fig. 11.

Antenna calibration using Three Antenna Method requires three antennas to form three antenna pairs, for which the SIL (Site Insertion Loss) is measured with the antennas positioned above a metal ground plane. In general, the ground plane influences the electrical characteristics of any antenna and its F_a , which varies with antenna height from the ground plane. Therefore, each of the three antennas shall be positioned at a specific height during the SIL measurements.

Each antenna pair is set so that centre point of both antennas are aligned. Prior to the measurement the VNA is compensated in an open, short, thru, load manner for VNA ports (full 2 port VNA calibration). VNA measurements are performed four times for each antenna pair to assess repeatability and set-up uncertainty. Before each measurement antenna pair is reassembled. Geometry parameters, radius, and distances are measured using calibrated distance meters.

Figure 11: Antenna setup for measurement by TAM with average magnetic field.

Mathematical model

Magnetic antenna factors for measured three antennas is calculated from Eqs. 19-21.

$$AF_{m1}(\omega) = \sqrt{\frac{-A_{23} \alpha_{12}\alpha_{13}}{A_{12}A_{13} \alpha_{23}}} \tag{19}$$

$$AF_{m2}(\omega) = \sqrt{\frac{-A_{13} \alpha_{21}\alpha_{23}}{A_{21}A_{23} \alpha_{13}}} \tag{20}$$

$$AF_{m3}(\omega) = \sqrt{\frac{-A_{12} \alpha_{31}\alpha_{32}}{A_{31}A_{32} \alpha_{12}}} \tag{21}$$

Magnetic antenna factor in the above equations is calculated from VNA measured transmissions between antenna pairs (A_{ij}) and their coupling factor (α_{ij}). Coupling factor between antenna pairs is calculated from Eqs. 22-33.

$$\alpha_{12} = \frac{\sqrt{1+k^2R_{12}^2}}{j\omega\mu_0\pi Z_L R_{12}^3} \left[1 + \frac{15}{8} \frac{(r_1r_2)^2}{R_{12}^4} + \frac{315}{64} \frac{(r_1r_2)^4}{R_{12}^8} \right] \tag{22}$$

$$\alpha_{23} = \frac{\sqrt{1+k^2R_{23}^2}}{j\omega\mu_0\pi Z_L R_{23}^3} \left[1 + \frac{15}{8} \frac{(r_2r_3)^2}{R_{23}^4} + \frac{315}{64} \frac{(r_2r_3)^4}{R_{23}^8} \right] \tag{23}$$

$$\alpha_{13} = \frac{\sqrt{1+k^2R_{13}^2}}{j\omega\mu_0\pi Z_L R_{13}^3} \left[1 + \frac{15}{8} \frac{(r_1r_3)^2}{R_{13}^4} + \frac{315}{64} \frac{(r_1r_3)^4}{R_{13}^8} \right] \tag{24}$$

$$\alpha_{21} = \frac{\sqrt{1+k^2 R_{21}^2}}{j\omega\mu_0\pi Z_L R_{21}^3} \left[1 + \frac{15}{8} \frac{(r_2 r_1)^2}{R_{21}^4} + \frac{315}{64} \frac{(r_2 r_1)^4}{R_{21}^8} \right] \quad (25)$$

$$\alpha_{31} = \frac{\sqrt{1+k^2 R_{31}^2}}{j\omega\mu_0\pi Z_L R_{31}^3} \left[1 + \frac{15}{8} \frac{(r_3 r_1)^2}{R_{31}^4} + \frac{315}{64} \frac{(r_3 r_1)^4}{R_{31}^8} \right] \quad (26)$$

$$\alpha_{32} = \frac{\sqrt{1+k^2 R_{32}^2}}{j\omega\mu_0\pi Z_L R_{32}^3} \left[1 + \frac{15}{8} \frac{(r_3 r_2)^2}{R_{32}^4} + \frac{315}{64} \frac{(r_3 r_2)^4}{R_{32}^8} \right] \quad (27)$$

$$R_{12} = \sqrt{d_{12}^2 + r_1^2 + r_2^2} \quad (28)$$

$$R_{23} = \sqrt{d_{23}^2 + r_2^2 + r_3^2} \quad (29)$$

$$R_{13} = \sqrt{d_{13}^2 + r_1^2 + r_3^2} \quad (30)$$

$$R_{21} = R_{12} \quad (31)$$

$$R_{31} = R_{13} \quad (32)$$

$$R_{32} = R_{23} \quad (33)$$

Definition of equation terms:

k	wave number $\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}\right)$
A_{ij}	transmission S-parameter between antennas
ω	angular frequency
μ_0	permeability of free space
Z_L	load impedance matched to the transmission line
r_i	radius of a loop antenna
d_{ij}	distances between these two loop antennas pair
α_{ij}	coupling factor between transmit antenna i and receive antenna j

For Eqs. 22-32 to be true the following conditions should be met: (1) both transmit antenna i and receive antenna j are circular loop antennas, (2) Eq. 34 and 35 should be satisfied.

$$k \sqrt{d_{ij}^2 + r_i^2 + r_j^2} \leq 1.0 \quad (34)$$

$$\frac{r_i r_j}{d_{ij}^2 + r_i^2 + r_j^2} \leq \frac{1}{16} \quad (35)$$

Uncertainty contributions of TAM

Distance and radius uncertainties (d , r)

Antenna calibration configurations are dependent on the following length parameters:

- Distance between antenna pair (d)
- Radius of each antenna (transmit and receive antenna) (r)

Radius is measured at inner part of loop antenna. Its uncertainty is estimated to be 3 mm. Rectangular uncertainty distribution can be assumed.

Distance between antenna pair is measured from centre to centre. Its uncertainty is estimated to be 5 mm. Rectangular uncertainty distribution can be assumed.

Uncertainty due to misalignment of antenna pairs

Antenna pair misalignment has two sources. The antenna pair can be misaligned due to misalignment in the angle between the antenna pairs and due to misalignment in the centre position.

Angle misalignment

Figure 12: Antenna position angle

Centre position misalignment

Additional uncertainty is added due to centre position misalignment of antenna pair centres as seen in Fig. 13. The Fig. 13 shows only misalignment in the z – direction from the centre position of the xz – plane.

Figure 13: Antenna par position in x - y sense

It is estimated the maximum misalignment uncertainty in the centre position is 10 mm for both directions. Rectangular probability distribution can be assumed. Misalignment in the angle between the antenna pair is assumed to be ± 5 degrees. Normal probability distribution can be assumed. The value of this uncertainty contribution can be estimated 0.2% of calculated coupling factor K .

Uncertainty due to the reflection from nearby object and the ground plane (Environment)

Uncertainty can be taken from the literature [7], where it is assumed the measurements uncertainty due to ground plane in the relevant frequency range is 1%. Rectangular uncertainty distribution can be assumed.

Uncertainty due to approximated equation of K

The uncertainty of the approximation is added to the calculated value of K . Its value is estimated to be 0.4% of the calculated F_a . This contribution can be assumed to have a normal probability distribution.

Distribution due to unevenness of magnetic field that interlinks with the loop area

Magnetic field F_a is defined when plane waves are incident. The magnetic field strength is constant, but it has phase delay vs. the loop lane, and that tendency becomes much stronger with larger radius of the receiving loop. On the other hand, when calibrating, average value of the magnetic field generated from the Standard placed opposite to and very near the AUC, and phase delay is not considered. Therefore, both differences are uncertain. Thus, the numerical integral to obtain the difference between when there was phase delay vs. when there was no phase delay and use that as uncertainty. For the probability distribution, the values obtained by calculation at worst case values providing the upper limit and lower limit, with a uniform distribution is considered. Typical uncertainty due to unevenness of magnetic field is around 0.5% of calculated antenna factor. Rectangular probability distribution can be assumed.

Uncertainty due to distribution of current conducting through TX antenna

The K is calculated under the assumption that the distribution of current conducting through the transmit antenna is constant, but actually, the larger the standard loop antenna is compared to the wavelength, that is, the higher the frequency, this leads to greater current distribution occurring, so electric field component occurs, and unneeded links to the AUC occur. This uncertainty can be taken from literature [7] and is estimated to be around 0.4% of calculated F_a . Rectangular probability distribution can be assumed.

Uncertainty of S_{21} measurement

Uncertainty is calculated using the same procedures as are relevant for S-parameter measurements. Typically, overall uncertainties are between 0.6 dB and 1 dB (normal distribution, $k=2$) and are higher for lower frequencies (noise).

3.4 A method using reference loop antenna

This method is primarily used for calibration of active receiving loop antenna, Fig. 14. Calibration is performed with reference loop antenna with already known F_a . This method has an advantage that it can ensure direct traceability to the national standard with only one measurement performed. Reference antenna (also called standard antenna) is used as transmitting antenna.

Measurement setup

Transmitting (standard) and receiving (DUT) loop antennas are placed over a ground plan with height h , distance d and with its centres aligned. The standard antenna is connected to VNA port 1, DUT antenna output is connected to VNA port 2, Fig 14.

Figure 14: A calibration method configuration using reference antenna

Mathematical model

Magnetic F_a for the measured antenna (AUC) along with the known antenna (STD) is calculated using Eqs. 36-38.

$$F_{aH}^{dB}(AUC) = -45.9 - 20\log_{10}(f_{MHz}) - S_{21}^{dB} + 20\log_{10}(K) - F_{aH}^{dB}(STD) \tag{36}$$

$$K = \frac{\sqrt{1+k^2 R_0^2}}{2\pi R_0^3} \left[1 + \frac{15}{8} \frac{(r_{STD} r_{AUC})^2}{R_0^4} + \frac{315}{64} \frac{(r_{STD} r_{AUC})^4}{R_0^8} \right] \tag{37}$$

$$R_0 = \sqrt{d_{STD,AUC}^2 + r_{STD}^2 + r_{AUC}^2} \tag{38}$$

For Eqs. 36-38 to be true the following conditions should be satisfied: (1) both AUC antenna and STD antenna are circular loop antennas, (2) Eqs. 39 and 40 should be satisfied.

$$k \sqrt{d_{STD,AUC}^2 + r_{AUC}^2 + r_{STD}^2} \leq 1.0 \tag{39}$$

$$\frac{r_{AUC} r_{STD}}{d_{STD,AUC}^2 + r_{STD}^2 + r_{AUC}^2} \leq \frac{1}{16} \tag{40}$$

- $F_{aH}^{dB}(AUC)$ antenna factor (magnetic) of DUT loop antenna in dB
- $F_{aH}^{dB}(STD)$ antenna factor (magnetic) of standard loop antenna in dB
- ω angular frequency ($2 \cdot \pi \cdot f$) in rad/s
- μ_0 Permeability of vacuum ($4 \cdot \pi \cdot 10^{-7}$ H/m)
- Z_L Characteristic impedance of measurement system (50 Ω)
- $d_{STD,AUC}$ distance between planes of Standards and AUC antennas in meters
- r_{STD} Loop radius of standard in meters
- r_{AUC} Loop radius of AUC in meters
- k wave number ($\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}$)
- S_{21}^{dB} absolute value of VNA measured transmission in dB

Contribution to standard uncertainties

$$F_{aH}^{dB}(AUC) = -45.9 - 20\log_{10}(f_{MHz}) - S_{21}^{dB} + 20\log_{10}(K) - F_{aH}^{dB}(STD) + k_{magnetic\ field} + k_{current} + k_{environment} \quad (41)$$

Uncertainty of AF of standard (reference) antenna

Antenna factor of F_a and its associated uncertainties are taken from calibration certificate. Probability distribution is normal with coverage factor 2. Other uncertainty sources have been explained already in the previous chapters. Typically, uncertainties for this method are 1.3 dB to 2 dB. Typically, the uncertainties are higher for lower frequencies (noise).

3.5 Traceability of TAM method and a method using reference loop antenna

Loop antennas are measured with VNA, which is calibrated before measurements using VNA calibration kit, that is calibrated in accredited national metrology institute. Loop antennas are then calibrated with Three Antenna Method or with relative calibration method, which uses reference loop antenna. Distance meters (e.g., electronic callipers) shall be also calibrated traceably.

4 Alternative methods for calibration of loop antennas

4.1 Calibration using Helmholtz coil

The F_a calibration of the loop antenna using TAM method or the method based on reference antenna might be problematic, especially at lower frequencies, because the loop antennas have generally lower sensitivities and therefore the reading on the VNA is very weak. As a result, the noise contribution becomes dominant, and the uncertainty of the F_a starts increasing quite significantly. To overcome this issue, a calibration of loop antenna in a Helmholtz coil might be a solution.

Figure 15: Calibration setup for generating magnetic field with Helmholtz coil using function generator and audio amplifier

The measuring setup based on Helmholtz coil is shown in Fig. 15. The function generator is connected to the audio amplifier, and the output of the amplifier is connected to the Helmholtz coil and Ampere meter which are connected in series. The magnetic field strength H_z in the centre of the coil is calculated from known geometries of the Helmholtz coils and measured current. The generated axial magnetic field H_z in A/m (*i.e.*, magnetic field strength along the z axis) in the centre of the coil is defined by Eq. 42, where $N_{1,2}$ denotes number of turns in coil 1 and 2, respectively, and I a common AC current driving the coils.

$$H_z = \frac{N_1 \cdot I \cdot r_1^2}{2(r_1^2 + a_1^2)^{3/2}} + \frac{N_2 \cdot I \cdot r_2^2}{2(r_2^2 + a_2^2)^{3/2}} \quad (42)$$

Parameters r_1 , r_2 , a_1 and a_2 are dimensional parameters of the Helmholtz coil as shown in Fig. 15. According to the definition of the Helmholtz coil the following simplification could be assumed:

- $r_1 = r_2 = r$,
- $N_1 = N_2 = N$ and
- $2 \times a_1 = 2 \times a_2 = r$.

The axial magnetic field H_z at the centre of the coil (point c in Fig. 15) is thus simplified, Eq. 43. Magnetic field density B_z is calculated from H_z using Eq. 44, where μ_0 denotes magnetic constant (*i.e.*, $\mu_0 = 4 \cdot \pi \cdot 10^{-7}$ Vs/Am). According to Eqs. 43 and 44 the AC current needs to be measured, number of turns needs to be counted, and the radius of the coil needs to be measured.

$$H_z = \frac{N \cdot I}{r \cdot (1,25)^{3/2}} \quad (43)$$

$$B_z = \mu_0 \cdot H_z \quad (44)$$

However, these equations are valid only for magnetic field strength H_z and magnetic field density B_z in the centre of the Helmholtz coil. However, the loop antennas are quite large therefore the homogeneity of the of the magnetic field strength and magnetic field density should not be neglected, Fig. 16.

Figure 16: Normalized axial - z (a) and radial - r (b) magnetic field within Helmholtz coil as a function of z and x. The B -fields were normalized with axial - z field at the centre of the coil. The orange squares denote the coils' windings.

To overcome this issue a magnetic field flux Φ_z through the calibrated loop antenna should be calculated instead, where r and N denotes the radius and the number of turns of the Helmholtz coil, respectively, b is the radius of the calibrated loop antenna, I is the current through the coil and a is the distance between the loop antenna and the coil, Eq. 45. The loop antenna is always placed at the centre of the Helmholtz coil therefore a equals half the distance between the coils. In the case of real Helmholtz coil Eq. 45 can be further simplified since the following expression is valid $r=2 \cdot a$, Eq. 46. To calculate average B_{avr} and H_{avr} , Eqs. 47 and 48 could be used, respectively.

$$\Phi_z = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot \mu_0 \cdot N \cdot I \cdot r^2 \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{r^2 + a^2}} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{r^2 + b^2 + a^2}} \right] \quad (45)$$

$$\Phi_z = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot \mu_0 \cdot N \cdot I \cdot r^2 \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{5 \cdot r^2 / 4}} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{5 \cdot r^2 / 4 + b^2}} \right] \quad (46)$$

$$B_{avr.} = \frac{\Phi_z}{\pi \cdot b^2} \quad (47)$$

$$H_{avr.} = \frac{\Phi_z}{\mu_0 \cdot \pi \cdot b^2} \quad (48)$$

When loop antenna is exposed to magnetic field, it produces an AC voltage at the output U_{out} (pay attention to the 50Ω termination of the output otherwise the output voltage is doubled). The F_a is defined by Eqs. 49 and 50, depending on whether the F_a is defined by the magnetic field strength or magnetic field density.

$$F_a = \frac{B_{avr.}}{U_{out}} \quad (49)$$

$$F_a = \frac{H_{avr.}}{U_{out}} \quad (50)$$

Uncertainty contributions:

- **Voltage reading from the loop antenna:** This value is an average of usually five voltage readings from the calibrated loop antenna. Type A uncertainty is estimated as half the difference between the maximal and minimal reading from the DUT.
- **Correction due to the voltage reading from the loop antenna:** The quantity corresponds to the least significant digit of the DUT display due to finite resolution of the display. The uncertainty is \pm half the resolution (half the magnitude of the least significant digit).
- **Vacuum permeability (μ_0):** This quantity is permeability of the vacuum. The value equals $4 \cdot \pi \cdot 10^{-7}$ H/m. The uncertainty of this quantity can be neglected.
- **Number of turns for a coil and corresponding uncertainty:** The number of turns can be precisely counted, therefore this correction and corresponding uncertainty is assumed 0. Some field distortion may arise at the beginning and at the end of coil windings, but uncertainty due to this effect is usually negligible.
- **The current through the coils (I):** This value is an average of usually at least ten readings from the amperemeter. The Type-A uncertainty is estimated to be a standard deviation of the mean of all readings. This uncertainty can be assumed to have normal distribution.
- **Correction of the current due to the specification of the amperemeter:** The uncertainty can be taken from the specifications. The uncertainty can have rectangular distribution.
- **Correction of the current due to the resolution of the amperemeter:** The uncertainty is \pm half the resolution of the amperemeter (half the magnitude of the least significant digit).
- **Helmholtz coil radius r and corresponding uncertainty:** This parameter is the mean radius of the Helmholtz coil that is measured with the calibrated ruler and Vernier calliper prior to DUT calibration.
- **Loop antenna radius b and corresponding uncertainty :** This parameter is the mean radius of the loop antenna and is measured with the calibrated ruler and Vernier calliper prior to calibration.
- **Correction due to inhomogeneity of the generated magnetic field:** The uncertainty is usually 1% of the generated B -field for most loop antennas
- **Correction of the generated field due to presence of the holder:** The holder might slightly influence the B -field, therefore additional correction should be included in the mathematical model. However, a Styrodur material is used as a holder which has a relative permeability $\mu_r \approx 1$ especially at lower frequencies ($f > 10$ kHz) therefore this correction and corresponding uncertainty could be neglected.
- **Correction of the generated field due to presence of the loop antenna:** The insertion of the loop antenna also influences generated magnetic field which is considered as additional correction. This uncertainty can be estimated to be 0.5% of the generated B -field.
- **Correction of the generated field due to presence of the background magnetic field:** In addition to the generated magnetic field, a 50 Hz bias magnetic field is usually present due to electrical installation and various loads near Helmholtz coil. This background B -field can be included as uncertainty contribution (defined by the measurement of background field when the current through the coil is zero). This correction is recommended only for calibration in frequency range $45 \text{ Hz} \leq f \leq 55 \text{ Hz}$.

4.2 Calibration using TEM cell

All loop antenna calibration methods described above (TAM method, method with a reference antenna or calibration using Helmholtz coil) do not produce perfectly homogeneous field where magnetic field lines would be perfectly parallel. To resolve this issue, loop antennas can be calibrated also in a TEM cell, Fig. 17. In this measuring setup, the signal generator is connected to the RF amplifier. The output of the amplifier is connected to the Port 1 of the TEM cell. Port 2 of the TEM cell is connected to the input of the attenuator while a RF power sensor is connected to the output of the attenuator. Alternatively (especially at higher frequencies), an RF coupler can be inserted between the RF amplifier and the input port of the TEM cell, while the output of the TEM cell is simply terminated by a high power 50 Ω termination.

The magnetic field strength in a TEM cell is calculated using Eq. 51, where the P denotes the net power in a TEM cell (roughly the power measured by the power sensor multiplied by the attenuation of the RF attenuator or the difference between the forward and reverse power which is measured by the RF coupler), d is the septum distance and Z_0 is impedance of free space (roughly 377 Ω). The output voltage of the loop antenna can be measured by digital multimeter (50 Ω feed thru should be also used to match the impedances), it can be measured by an oscilloscope or even by power sensor at higher frequencies.

Figure 17: Calibration setup for generating magnetic field strength in TEM cell

$$H_s = \frac{\sqrt{P \cdot Z}}{d \cdot Z_0} \quad (51)$$

$$F_a = \frac{H_s}{U_{out}} \quad (52)$$

$$F_a = \frac{B_s}{U_{out}} \quad (53)$$

The F_a is calculated using Eqs. 52 and 53, depending on the definition of the F_a . Uncertainty calculation includes the following contributions:

- **uncertainty of the voltage measurement:**
 - DMM method: type-A, specification, resolution, effect of matching 50 Ω feed thru
 - Oscilloscope method: type-A, specification, resolution
 - Power sensor: type-A, specification, resolution, mismatch, uncertainty of attenuation of used
- **uncertainty of net power measurements of the TEM cell:** type-A, resolution, specification, calibration factor of the power sensor and corresponding uncertainty, uncertainty of attenuator, mismatch between power sensor and attenuator with corresponding uncertainty, *etc.*)
- **uncertainty associated to the septum distance**
- uncertainty due to the **deviation of the magnetic field strength when the loop antenna is inserted** in a TEM cell
- uncertainty due to the deviation of the magnetic field strength when the **loop antenna holder** is placed in a TEM cell
- uncertainty due to **inhomogeneity** of the magnetic field strength

The TEM cell can be only used in a TEM mode where electric field E and magnetic field H are both perpendicular to the direction of propagation (*i.e.*, no field component in the direction of travel). At low frequencies, only the TEM mode exists, but at higher frequencies the cell dimensions become comparable to the wavelength and TE and TM modes (*i.e.*, non-TEM modes) can propagate and the field inside the cell becomes non-uniform and unpredictable. The maximal frequency depends on the septum distance, and it can be by the rule of thumb estimated as $f_{max} = c/(2 \cdot d)$, where c denoted the speed of light and d largest cross-sectional dimension of the cell. Typically, the upper frequency limits are 400 MHz and 900 MHz for TEM cells having 20 cm and 10 cm septum distances, respectively.

Moreover, the TEM should be neither used at very low frequencies although the free space impedance 377Ω is in principle valid. This relation between the E and H should be used only when both quantities are in the far-field (*i.e.*, plane wave conditions) while this is not the case when frequencies below 9 kHz are used (E and H fields are not tightly coupled fields become quasi-static, coupling becomes: mostly capacitive E -field or inductive H -field, the TEM cell no longer behaves like a uniform transmission line, field uniformity degrades and the calibration based on 377Ω assumption becomes less meaningful). Therefore, the loop antennas can be calibrated in a TEM cell above 9 kHz due to low frequency constrains, while on contrary the highest operation frequency of the loop antenna is usually well below the frequency limit of the TEM cell therefore high frequency limit usually does not apply.

5 Conclusions

This deliverable has presented improved calibration methods for monopole and loop antennas used in low-frequency electromagnetic compatibility measurements. The work has addressed both the theoretical basis and the practical implementation of the selected methods, with particular attention to measurement uncertainty, traceability, and applicability under realistic laboratory conditions.

For monopole antennas, the Equivalent Capacitance Substitution Method has been shown to provide a practical and effective calibration approach for antennas that satisfy the required dimensional and frequency-related conditions. The method enables calibration of the antenna matching unit by replacing the radiating rod with an equivalent capacitance representing the self-capacitance of the monopole. The study has demonstrated that the quality of the calibration result depends strongly on the correct realization of the dummy adapter, the suitability of the selected equivalent capacitance, and the control of measurement conditions such as grounding, mismatch, and connector arrangement. The work has also confirmed that the method is not universally applicable, and that plane-wave calibration remains necessary for antennas whose geometry or intended use falls outside the valid range of the substitution approach.

For loop antennas, the deliverable has shown that the Three Antenna Method provides a viable absolute calibration method in the low-frequency range, provided that the geometrical parameters of the antennas are well known and that alignment and environmental conditions are adequately controlled. The method based on a reference loop antenna has also been identified as a useful practical alternative when a calibrated standard is available. In addition, the investigation of Helmholtz coil and TEM cell methods has demonstrated the value of complementary calibration approaches, particularly in frequency ranges where weak coupling, poor sensitivity, or increased uncertainty limit the performance of the Three Antenna Method. The results therefore support a method-selection strategy based on frequency range, antenna type, and required uncertainty rather than the use of a single method for all cases.

A significant outcome of the work is the systematic evaluation of uncertainty contributions for each calibration approach. For monopole antennas, the dominant influences include the choice of equivalent capacitance, voltage measurement effects, mismatch, and effective height estimation. For loop antennas, important contributions arise from dimensional measurements, antenna alignment, environmental effects, model approximations, and transmission measurement sensitivity. The deliverable has shown that careful design of the calibration setup and proper selection of the method can significantly reduce the overall uncertainty and improve the reproducibility of the calibration result.

The work has also reinforced the importance of traceability in antenna calibration. The proposed methods are linked to calibrated dimensional, capacitance, impedance, and transmission measurements, and where relevant to reference antennas or controlled field-generating systems. This provides metrological basis for the reported antenna factors and supports their use in accredited calibration and EMC measurement activities.

Overall, the deliverable contributes to improved harmonisation of low-frequency antenna calibration practice by providing technically justified and practically applicable procedures for monopole and loop antennas. The methods and analyses presented in this work support more reliable and comparable antenna factor determinations across laboratories and provide a useful basis for further development of traceable EMC antenna calibration capabilities.

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